

SOME BASIC PROBLEMS IN THE ANALYSIS OF
INSTABILITY FOR COMPOSITE CYLINDRICAL SHELLS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper some basic problems in the analysis of nonlinear instability for multilayered composite cylindrical shells are discussed. These problems are : the influences of initial imperfections and geometrical nonlinearities of shells ; the effects of physical nonlinearity caused by the material nonlinearity of shear modulus, the influences of transverse shearing deformation and the effects of prebuckling deformations on buckling and postbuckling behavior of laminated composite cylindrical shells under various boundary conditions . All these influences are studied under various loading conditions : e.g. axial compression, hydrostatic pressure, and torsion . Of course the interaction of these influences is an important and complicated problem. This paper is a report for the synthetic analysis of these influences that based on a series of our investigated results in the recent years [1-5] .

INTRODUCTION

Thin shell structures constructed by multilayered fiber-reinforced composite shells are widely used in aeronautical and astronautical engineering constructions in recent years. Because of the anisotropic property of the shell laminates as well as both the physical and geometrical nonlinearities of the composite materials and the complex behavior during buckling, to solve the instability problem of such shells is very complicated. At the beginning of 70's, Khot and Venkaya^[6-8] first proposed a method to consider the geometrical nonlinearity and the initial postbuckling behavior of the composite shells during buckling. Afterward

Tennyson made a synthetic review about this field(ref.[9]). During this period, refer to the influences caused by the physical nonlinearity of the composite material to the shell buckling, only R.M.Jones and H.T.Hahn contributed some reports for the cases of composite plates under compression [10,11]. In our works [1,2,4], we used the nonlinear stress-strain relations proposed by H.T.Hahn and S.Tsai [12]. The physical nonlinearity is induced mainly by the nonlinear effect of shear modulus of composite materials. For the study of geometrical nonlinearity and the initial imperfections of the composite shells, Karman-Donnell Equations and the Donnell's initial imperfection factor were used. The governing equations were solved by the energy method and the finite-difference method proposed by our paper [13]. The laminated cylindrical shells considered are with symmetric and antisymmetric angle-ply reinforced fibers as well as any ply-angle orientation. Computed results show the initial postbuckling equilibrium configuration curves of composite shells and also the influences of coupling effects and number of layers on the value of critical loads of the laminated cylindrical shells under axial compression, hydrostatic pressure and torsion. In Fig.1, two and four layers boron/epoxy cylindrical shells are computed. The results show that the existence of nonlinearity of the shearing modulus will usually cause the buckling loads to decrease significantly, in spite of whether the material of the shell is linear or nonlinear elastic. In Fig.2, the postbuckling equilibrium configuration curves ($P-w/h$) of shells with $/30^\circ/-30^\circ/0^\circ/$ plying case under axial compression are given. Results show that such shells are very sensitive to the initial imperfections. Also, the physical nonlinearity of

Fig. 1 Axial Buckling load of boron/epoxy shells

Fig. 2 Axial buckling curves of $/30^\circ/-30^\circ/0^\circ/$ boron/epoxy shells

of the material will render the shells to be less sensitive to the initial imperfections during buckling. These computed results are well confirmed by some experimental data.

The transverse shear deformation has important influence on buckling behavior of laminated composite shells. In work [3], we consider the interaction between the effect of transverse shear deformation and nonlinearity of both shear modulus of the material and initial imperfections of these composite shells. Analytical results show that for multilayered composite shells the transverse shear effect on buckling and postbuckling behavior must not be ignored.

The investigations got by Stein and Almroth [14,15] show that the prebuckling curvature induced by the boundary bending effect will result the critical buckling load to be lower than the classical buckling load. However, in the laminated cylindrical shells, besides the boundary effect there are also the coupling effect that will influence the prebuckling curvature and will act as a prominent effect on the buckling load. These mutual interactions between the boundary bending effect and the coupling effect has to be thoroughly investigated. R.M.Jones [16] had studied about this problem and got a series of valuable conclusions. His investigation is limited in a boundary condition of simply supported S2 case. In paper [5], we study this problem in more general cases, eight cases of boundary conditions are considered: e.g. four simply supported cases S1, S2, S3, S4, and four clamped cases C1, C2, C3, C4. The loading conditions considered include axial compression, lateral pressure, hydrostatic pressure and torsion. The nonlinear governing equations are solved by the series method and the finite-difference method. Some important conclusions are obtained from the numerical results.

Refer to the analysis of initial postbuckling and the application of Koiter's Theory, some discussions are made in the work [17].

EFFECTS OF THE GEOMETRICAL NONLINEARITY OF THE SHELL AND THE NONLINEARITY OF THE COMPOSITE MATERIALS DURING BUCKLING

The strain-displacement equations used are as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} e_x &= u_{o,x} - z w_{,xx} + (\lambda/2) \cdot (w_{,x})^2 \\ e_y &= v_{o,y} - z w_{,yy} + (\lambda/2) \cdot (w_{,y})^2 - (1/R) \cdot (1 + (z/R)) w \\ \gamma_{xy} &= u_{o,y} + v_{o,x} - 2z(w_{,xy}) + \lambda (w_{,x})(w_{,y}) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\lambda=1+2(w_0/w)$ is the Donnell's initial imperfection factor, w_0 is the initial deflection of the laminated cylindrical shell.

In order to study the physical nonlinearity of the composite material we use the nonlinear stress-strain relations as follows [12] :

$$\begin{Bmatrix} e_1 \\ e_2 \\ e_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & 0 \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} + S_{6666} \tau_{12}^2 \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \tau_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

When the reinforced fibers are in arbitrary angle-ply cases, the Eqs. of the laminated cylindrical shell buckling are [2] :

$$L_1(w) - L_2(F) = N_x w_{,xx} + N_y w_{,yy} + 2 N_{xy} w_{,xy} \quad (3)$$

$$L_2(w) + L_3(F) = (w_{,xy})^2 - (w_{,xx}) \cdot (w_{,yy})$$

where operators L_1, L_2, L_3 are defined as :

$$L_1() = d_{11}(),_{xxxx} + 4d_{16}(),_{xxyy} + (2d_{12} + d_{66})(),_{xxyy} + 4d_{26}(),_{xyyy} + d_{22}(),_{yyyy}$$

$$L_2() = b_{21}(),_{xxxx} + (2b_{26} - b_{61})(),_{xxyy} + (b_{11} + b_{22} - 2b_{66})(),_{xxyy}$$

$$+ (2b_{16} - b_{62})(),_{xyyy} + b_{12}(),_{yyyy} - (1/R)(),_{xx}$$

$$L_3() = a_{22}(),_{xxxx} - 2a_{26}(),_{xxyy} + (2a_{12} + a_{66})(),_{xxyy} - 2a_{16}(),_{xyyy} + a_{11}(),_{yyyy}$$

In the above Eqs. F is the Airy Stress Function :

$$N_x = F_{,yy}, \quad N_y = F_{,xx}, \quad N_{xy} = -F_{,xy} \quad (4)$$

For nonlinear Eqs.(3), it's hard to get the closed solution, thus in [2,4] the energy method and finite-difference method are used. According to the energy method, suppose the deflection function w is :

$$w_n = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} [A_{2i-1} \sin(ny/R) + A_{2i} \cos(ny/R)] \sin(i\pi x/L) \quad (5)$$

The above function can satisfy the boundary condition of $w = 0$. Substitute w into the Eqs. of compatibility, then the stress function F can be found:

$$F_n = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} [(B_{4i-3} \sin(i\pi x/L) + B_{4i-2} \cos(i\pi x/L)) \sin(ny/R) + (B_{4i-1} \sin(i\pi x/L) + B_{4i} \cos(i\pi x/L)) \cos(ny/R) + (N_x y^2 + N_y x^2) / 2 - N_{xy} xy] \quad (6)$$

here the coefficients $B_{4i-3}, B_{4i-2}, B_{4i-1}, B_{4i}$ are given in paper [2].

The expression of total energy of the system can thus be formed :

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi = & (1/2) \int_0^{2\pi R} \int_0^L (\{N\}^T [a] \{N\} + \{\chi\}^T [d] \{\chi\}) dx dy \\ & + (1/2) \int_0^{2\pi R} \int_0^L [N_x (w_{,x})^2 + N_y (w_{,y})^2 + 2N_{xy} (w_{,x})(w_{,y})] dx dy \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

The expressions of energy function Π in detail are listed in papers [2,4].

From the variation of the total energy Π , we can get the equilibrium Eqs. (ref.[13]). In the numerical computation, the truncated trigonometrical series must contain the main terms that can represent the buckling wave form during shell buckling. In work [2], when use central finite-difference method, usually take more than 50 nodes can get satisfactory results. In papers [1,2,4], we use these methods to compute various types of composite cylindrical shells under different loading conditions (axial compression, hydrostatic pressure, torsion), the results are rather good when in compare with other theoretical methods or with experimental data.

THE EFFECT OF TRANSVERSE SHEAR DEFORMATION
ON THE NONLINEAR BUCKLING OF SHELLS

Recent studies show that for multilayered composite shells the transverse shear effect on the analysis of stress or strain and instability is an important factor^[3,9]. In this investigation, usually the transverse shear stresses τ_{xz} and τ_{yz} are supposed to be a parabolic function, and these shear stresses are assumed to be zero at the shell surfaces. Thus the transverse shear forces Q_x and Q_y are defined as :

$$Q_x = \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{h_{k-1}}^{h_k} \tau_{xz}^{(k)} dz, \quad Q_y = \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{h_{k-1}}^{h_k} \tau_{yz}^{(k)} dz, \quad \begin{Bmatrix} Q_x \\ Q_y \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{55} & A_{45} \\ A_{45} & A_{44} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

$$A_{ij} = \frac{5}{4} \sum_{k=1}^n \bar{Q}_{ij}^{(k)} \left[h_k - h_{k-1} - \frac{4}{3} \frac{(h_k^3 - h_{k-1}^3)}{h^2} \right], \quad (i, j = 4, 5) \quad (9)$$

The transverse shear strains γ_{xz} and γ_{yz} are

$$\gamma_{xz} = \phi_x(x, y) + w_{,x}, \quad \gamma_{yz} = \phi_y(x, y) + w_{,y} \quad (10)$$

where ϕ_x and ϕ_y are rotational components for the normals of the shell surface rotate about the directions of x and y respectively. The transverse shear stresses of each layer computed by the following formulas :

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{yz} \end{Bmatrix}_{(k)} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{55} & \bar{Q}_{45} \\ \bar{Q}_{45} & \bar{Q}_{44} \end{bmatrix}_{(k)} \begin{Bmatrix} w_{,x} + \phi_x \\ w_{,y} + \phi_y \end{Bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

If the above Eq. is multiplied by the parabolic weight function, the shear stress at the shell surfaces is zero, but the shearing stresses between layers are discontinuous. Work [18] proposed through complimentary energy principle that the shear stresses distribution is parabolic over the thickness of each layer and is continuous at the interfaces. Thus get the shear

rigidity represented by the following coefficients :

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_{44} &= a/(ab-c^2), & A_{55} &= b/(ab-c^2), & A_{45} &= c/(ab-c^2) \\
 a &= \frac{9}{4h^2} \sum_{k=1}^n (\bar{Q}_{44}^{(k)} / [\Delta \bar{Q}]^2) H_k, & b &= \frac{9}{4h^2} \sum_{k=1}^n (\bar{Q}_{55}^{(k)} / [\Delta \bar{Q}]^2) H_k \\
 c &= \frac{9}{4h^2} \sum_{k=1}^n (\bar{Q}_{45}^{(k)} / [\Delta \bar{Q}]^2) H_k, & [\Delta \bar{Q}]^2 &= \bar{Q}_{44}^{(k)} \bar{Q}_{55}^{(k)} - [\bar{Q}_{45}^{(k)}]^2 \\
 H_k &= h_k - h_{k-1} - \frac{8}{3} \frac{h_k^3 - h_{k-1}^3}{h^2} + \frac{16}{5} \frac{h_k^5 - h_{k-1}^5}{h^4}
 \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

The results computed by Eqs.(9) and (12) show that the buckling load of the former is a bit higher than that of the latter (see in Fig.3 where 4 points denoted by *). The assumption made by [18] is more reasonable, so we take Eq.(12) to consider the effect of transverse shear. The equations of equilibrium and compatibility are as follows :

$$\begin{aligned}
 -A_{55} (\phi_{x,x} + w_{,x}) + D_{11} \phi_{x,xx} + D_{12} \phi_{y,xy} + D_{66} (\phi_{x,yy} + \phi_{y,xy}) &= 0 \\
 -A_{44} (\phi_{y,y} + w_{,y}) + D_{22} \phi_{y,yy} + D_{12} \phi_{x,xy} + D_{66} (\phi_{x,xy} + \phi_{y,xx}) &= 0 \\
 D_{11} \phi_{x,xxx} + (D_{12} + 2D_{66}) (\phi_{x,xyy} + \phi_{y,xyx}) + D_{22} \phi_{y,yyy} - (F_{,xx} / R) + F_{,yy} (w_{,xx} + \bar{w}_{,xx}) \\
 - 2F_{,xy} (w_{,xy} + w_{,xy}) + F_{,xx} (w_{,yy} + \bar{w}_{,yy}) &= 0 \\
 a_{11} F_{,yyyy} + (2a_{12} + a_{66}) F_{,xxyy} + a_{22} F_{,xxxx} = w_{,xy}^2 - w_{,xx} w_{,yy} + 2w_{,xy} \bar{w}_{,xy} - w_{,xx} \bar{w}_{,yy} \\
 - \bar{w}_{,xx} w_{,yy} + (w_{,xx} / R) &
 \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

To solve the Eqs.(13), only the principal term of the buckling wave is taken as the wave form of the initial imperfection :

$$\bar{w} = \bar{w}_0 = \bar{\xi}_1 h \cos \alpha x \cos \beta y \tag{14}$$

where $\alpha = m\pi/L$, $\beta = n/R$, integers m and n are buckling waves correspond to the classical linear critical pressure, L is the length of the shell. The wave function of the buckling is taken as :

$$w/h = \xi_1 \cos \alpha x \cos \beta y + \xi_2 \cos 2\alpha x + \xi_3 \cos 4\alpha x + \xi_4 \cos 2\alpha x \cos 2\beta y + \xi_5 \cos 2\beta y \tag{15}$$

Use $\cos \alpha x \cos \beta y$, $\cos 2\alpha x$, $\cos 4\alpha x$, $\cos 2\alpha x \cos 2\beta y$ as weight functions to integrate by Galerkin method, then get a set of nonlinear equilibrium Eqs., and from these nonlinear equations we use iteration method to obtain the final critical compressive load. Fig.3 and Fig.4 are the computed results that show the effects of transverse shear on the axial buckling load. Fig.5 shows the effects of initial imperfections on axial buckling load.

The effect of prebuckling deformations on buckling of laminated composite cylindrical shells under various boundary conditions is investigated by Nonlinear Prebuckling Consistent Theory. Here, the coupling effect is not only included in the buckling equations, but also entering the prebuckling governing equations which satisfy all the boundary conditions and the rigorous prebuckling deformations. Up to now, the influence of the prebuckling curvature induced by the mutual interaction of the coupling effect and the boundary bending effect has not been thoroughly investigated. In our work [5], we use the following large deflection equations :

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_{x_0} &= u_{0,x} + (1/2)(w_{0,x})^2 & ; & \quad \xi_{y_0} = w_0/R & ; & \quad \gamma_{xy_0} = v_{0,x} \\ k_x &= -w_{0,xx} & ; & \quad k_y = k_{xy} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

When the shell is under the action of axial compression or hydrostatic pressure or torsion, the prebuckling curvature and stresses are all symmetric to the axis of the shell, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} u_0 &= u_0(x) & ; & \quad v_0 = v_0(x) & ; & \quad w_0 = w_0(x) \\ N_x &= N_x(x) & ; & \quad N_y = N_y(x) & ; & \quad N_{xy} = N_{xy}(x) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

The stress-strain relations are :

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \delta N \\ \delta M \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} [A] & [B] \\ [B] & [D] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta \xi_0 \\ \delta k \end{Bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

Note that stress function $F_{,xx} = N_y$, then we can get the equilibrium Eqs. expressed by deflection function w_0 :

$$w_{0,xxxx} + 4S w_{0,xx} + 4T^2 (w_0 - w_p) = 0 \quad (19)$$

where,

$$S = -(2b_{21} + \bar{N}_x a_{22} R) / 4(a_{22} d_{11} + b_{21}^2) R$$

$$T^2 = [4R^2(a_{22} d_{11} + b_{21}^2)]$$

$$w_p = R(a_{22} \bar{N}_x + a_{26} \bar{N}_{xy}) + R^2 a_{22} q$$

here q is the external pressure. Introduce the following non-dimensional parameters \bar{w} , \bar{F} , x_1 , y_1 :

$$\bar{w} = w / (a_{22} d_{22})^{1/2} & ; & \quad \bar{F} = F (a_{11} / a_{22})^{1/2} & ;$$

$$x_1 = x / (4R^2 d_{11} a_{22})^{1/4} & ; & \quad y_1 = y / (4R^2 d_{22} a_{22})^{1/4}$$

The buckling equations of the cylindrical shell are :

$$\begin{aligned} L_1(\delta \bar{w}) - L_2(\delta \bar{F}) &= \bar{F}_{,y_1 y_1} \delta \bar{w}_{,x_1 x_1} + \bar{F}_{,x_1 x_1} \delta \bar{w}_{,y_1 y_1} - 2\bar{F}_{,x_1 y_1} \delta \bar{w}_{,x_1 y_1} + \bar{w}_{,x_1 x_1} \delta \bar{F}_{,y_1 y_1} \\ L_2(\delta \bar{w}) + L_3(\delta \bar{F}) &= -\bar{w}_{,x_1 x_1} \delta \bar{w}_{,y_1 y_1} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

In the above governing Eqs.(20), operators L_1 , L_2 , L_3 are :

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_1(\cdot) &= (\phi/4)(\cdot)_{,x_1x_1x_1} + \gamma(\cdot)_{,x_1x_1x_1} + (\rho/2)(\cdot)_{,x_1x_1x_1} + \zeta(\cdot)_{,x_1x_1x_1} + (\phi/4)(\cdot)_{,y_1y_1y_1} \\
 L_2(\cdot) &= k(\cdot)_{,x_1x_1x_1} + \psi(\cdot)_{,x_1x_1x_1} + \xi(\cdot)_{,x_1x_1x_1} + \bar{\lambda}(\cdot)_{,y_1y_1y_1}^{-2}(\cdot)_{,x_1x_1} \quad (21) \\
 L_3(\cdot) &= (4/\phi)(\cdot)_{,x_1x_1x_1} - \beta(\cdot)_{,x_1x_1x_1} + 4\alpha(\cdot)_{,x_1x_1x_1} - \delta(\cdot)_{,x_1x_1x_1} + 4\phi(\cdot)_{,y_1y_1y_1}
 \end{aligned}$$

Let
$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{\delta w} &= w_1(x) \sin(ny/r) + w_2(x) \cos(ny/r) \\
 \bar{\delta F} &= f_1(x) \sin(ny/r) + f_2(x) \cos(ny/r)
 \end{aligned}
 \quad (22)$$

Partial differential equations(20) can be transformed into ordinary differential equations by using Eqs.(22), and can be solved by finite-difference method with equal intervals. All these parameters : $\phi, \gamma, \rho, \zeta, k, \psi, \xi, \bar{\lambda}$, etc. are listed in paper [5]. Comparison of buckling test data with theoretical results for three layers glass/epoxy cylindrical shells under axial compression is listed in the following table, in which the unit of buckling load is in Newton(N).

No.	ply-angle θ°			Test	Theo.	Ser.	F-D	F-D	Comp. of Theo. & Test			
	int	mid	ext	P	P _t	P _s	P _{α_1}	P _{α_2}	P/P _t	P/P _s	P/P _{α_1}	P/P _{α_2}
1a	-70°	70°	0°	26077	38400	34980	35336	30428	0.679	0.745	0.738	0.860
2a	-20°	20°	90°	24607	39932	36115	35764	35670	0.616	0.681	0.688	0.690
4a	90°	-45°	45°	24874	36864	36619	36155	32878	0.674	0.679	0.688	0.757
4b	90°	-45°	45°	22603	36147	35358	35554	32650	0.625	0.639	0.636	0.692
9a	0°	-45°	45°	25898	32490	30619	30651	30660	0.795	0.846	0.845	0.845
9b	0°	-45°	45°	24696	33759	32690	31956	32953	0.732	0.755	0.773	0.749
11a	30°	90°	30°	26121	36267	36721	35652	34681	0.720	0.711	0.733	0.753
11b	30°	90°	30°	27769	36115	36521	35942	34298	0.769	0.760	0.773	0.810
12a	30°	90°	-30°	25453	36245	33412	33501	31889	0.703	0.762	0.760	0.798
12b	30°	90°	-30°	25186	39276	35554	36276	30625	0.641	0.708	0.694	0.822

In above table the test data is given by paper [19], in which there is a theoretical solution denoted by P_t, where the proposed deflection function is simple and rough so can't include the coupling and edge effect. We take more terms for a series of deflection function and get the solution P_s, that is better than P_t in compare with the test data. P_t is computed by the membrane prebuckling theory, and P_s is computed by prebuckling consistent theory. Here, P _{α_2} is better than other results. Fig.6 shows the influence of prebuckling deformations on torsional buckling load of symmetric angle-ply cylindrical shells. Fig.7 shows the buckling load of external pressure for two layers angle-ply shells under various boundary conditions. Other results are shown in detail in paper [5].

SOME NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. For boron/epoxy shells under axial compression and hydrostatic pressure, the numerical results show that :

(a) For angle-ply case, the coupling effect will fade away rapidly as the number of layers increases. In the case of four layers, critical pressure will be 9% lower than the case without coupling effect, and for eight layers, the load is only 1.7% lower. For the case of odd number layers, only tension-shear coupling effect is happened, its max. influence on the critical load only 3.3%, happened in the case of 3 layers;

(b) when ply-angle is not near 0° or 90° , the effect of nonlinearity for shear modulus decrease the critical load. In most cases such nonlinearity will decrease the effect of coupling rigidity on the critical load.

(c) The effect of nonlinearity of shear modulus on critical load of hydrostatic pressure is much less than that on axial compression. Numerical results show that even if the shell is 5 times thicker than that for the case of axial compression, the effect of such nonlinearity on the critical load is still less than the case of axial compression. For the case of the angle-ply, when $\theta \geq 60^\circ$, such effect of nonlinearity can be neglected.

(d) For the case of angle-ply [$30^\circ/-30^\circ/0^\circ$] under axial compression, it is rather sensitive to the initial imperfection. But the effect of nonlinearity of shear modulus will decrease the sensitivity of initial imperfection for cylindrical shells under axial compression.

(e) The effect of nonlinearity of shear modulus is important for the torsional buckling of composite cylindrical shells. Here, the most severe nonlinear effect is happened in the case of ply-angle 90° . For boron/epoxy shells with $R/h=50$, the critical torque would be decreased more than 50%. Even for $R/h=100$, will still decrease 40%. For carbon/epoxy shells with $R/h=50$, the critical torque will decrease about 34%.

2. When L/R of the shell is decreasing and the modulus ratio E_1/E_2 is increasing, the effect of transverse shear will increase rapidly. For high modulus ratio shells, critical loads will decrease significantly, here the effect of transverse shear is noticeable. In general, the degree of influence from the effect of transverse shear depends upon various factors, e.g. $L/R, R/h, E_1/E_2, E_{12}/E_2$, and G_{23}/E_2 of the shells.

3. The effects of prebuckling curvature on the buckling load are :

(a) For symmetric ply $\theta=30^\circ$ and antisymmetric ply $\theta=40^\circ$, when increasing in layers, the buckling load will also increase, and thus effects of prebuckling are also increasing. For shells with single or double layer this effect will increase as the increasing of modulus ratio. For the shell with 3 or 4 layers, this effect will increase at the first, then when E_1/E_2 is sufficiently large will decrease again.

(b) Prebuckling effect will fade away rapidly as the length of the shell increases. In hydrostatic pressure case, this effect can be neglected for cylindrical shells with middle length.

(c) For angle-ply single layer shells, when θ approaches 45° , the prebuckling effect will make torsional buckling loads to decrease about 8%.

(d) For antisymmetric angle-ply shell $[\theta^\circ/-\theta^\circ]$, critical load can be decreased 14% by the prebuckling effect for S2 condition. For other boundary conditions the decreasing will be less than that of S2 case.

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Fig.3 Effects of transverse shear on the axial buckling load

Fig.4 Effects of transverse shear on the axial buckling load

Fig.5 Effects of initial imperfections on buckling loads

Fig.6 Influence of prebuckling deformations on torsional buckling load of symmetric angle-ply cylindrical shells.

Fig.7 Buckling load of external pressure for two layers angle-ply cylindrical shells under various boundary conditions .